

Copulas in Atlantic Creoles and Other Languages

Cópulas nos crioulos atlânticos e em outras línguas

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Abstract: In his first linguistics paper, Holm (1976) linked African American English (AAE) to the Atlantic creoles through the deletion rates of AAE copulas as described in Labov (1969, 1972) and then linked the copula pattern in the creoles to that of Yoruba, eventually convincing Labov (1982) of the validity of this link. Holm expanded his study of Atlantic creole copula patterns in his 1988 survey of creole syntactic features, adding to this patterns in non-Atlantic creoles in Holm *et al.* (1999) and Holm and Patrick, eds. (2007). Now, with the publication of the *Atlas of Pidgin and Creole Structures* in 2013, the present study is able to offer the broadest perspective yet on this area of syntax that demonstrates that creole languages can be considerably more complex than their lexifiers. The article concludes by proposing new criteria for classifying the Atlantic creoles as a typological group.

Keywords: African American English; APiCS; Atlantic Creoles.

Resumo: Em seu primeiro artigo, Holm (1976) relacionou o inglês afro-americano (AAE) aos crioulos atlânticos através do apagamento das cópulas do AAE como descritas por Labov (1969, 1972) e então ligou o padrão das cópulas dos crioulos

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ao encontrado no iorubá, finalmente convencendo Labov (1982) da validade desse elo. Holm, em seu estudo de caso dos traços sintáticos dos crioulos de 1988, expandiu seu trabalho sobre o padrão da cópula nos crioulos atlânticos, incluindo também os crioulos não-atlânticos (Holm *et al.* 1999) e Holm and Patrick, eds. (2007). Agora, com a publicação do *Atlas of Pidgin and Creole Structures* em 2013, o presente estudo oferece uma perspectiva mais ampla sobre essa área da sintaxe que demonstra que as línguas crioulas podem ser consideravelmente mais complexas do que suas línguas lexificadoras. Por fim, o artigo propõe novos critérios para a classificação dos crioulos atlânticos como um grupo tipológico.

Palavras-chave: Inglês afro-americano; APiCS; Crioulos Atlânticos.

1 Introduction

I began my doctoral studies in linguistics at the University of London in 1975 after having taught English for several years in the United States in downtown Detroit, which had suddenly become overwhelmingly black because of white flight to the suburbs after the 1967 race riots. Having been trained in teaching English as a foreign language, I realized that linguistics could help explain why many of my students whose usual speech variety was African American English (AAE) had real problems in writing standard English, and I went to London hoping to get a better understanding of their problems. I had had some contact with Caribbean Creole English, which seemed to share many features with AAE, and I had read Dillard's 1972 book claiming that the two were related to one another and possibly to the languages of Africa, a position called "the creole hypothesis". However, this was not the general view of what was then called Negro Non-standard English, which was widely attributed simply to a lack of education. William Labov, America's leading sociolinguist and expert on African American English, had stated quite plainly, "We must recognize that youth growing up in the inner cities today is not in contact with that Creole continuum" (Labov 1972: 66).

2 Copula variability on the Afro-American continuum

I decided to write my doctoral dissertation on the Creole English of Nicaragua, which I had first encountered as a teenager. On my way to Nicaragua to do fieldwork in 1976, I went to Guyana to give my first linguistics paper at a meeting of the Society for Caribbean Linguistics, held at the University of Guyana near Georgetown. My paper (Holm 1976) was an attempt to link Labov's 1969 and 1972 quantitative studies of AAE copula variability to the creolist hypothesis that AAE, Caribbean Creole English and their substrate African languages were interrelated. This paper was later revised and published with an afterword (Holm 1984). In it I pointed out that "Labov found there was a correlation between the probability of a copula's deletion and the syntactic environment following the copula: 'The least deletion and contraction take place before a following noun phrase; more occur before predicate adjectives' (1972: 87)'" (Holm 1976: 2). Bickerton had found the same pattern of copula deletion in Guyanese Creole English; to see if this pattern could be found in other creoles, I did a quantitative analysis of one text in Jamaican and another in Gullah and found that the deletion rate of copulas followed the same pattern (Holm 1976: 2). I suggested this reflected part of a pattern found in African languages: "Homburger (1949: 150-1) points out that a distinction must be made in discussing African 'copulas' before various following syntactic environments such as (A) noun phrases, (B) adjectives, (C) become, and (D) locatives. 'Many languages do not use a copula in (B) forms... most languages have distinctive words for A, B, and D'" (Holm 1976: 3). In other words, the low deletion rate (or frequent presence) of the copula before predicate nouns in African American creoles and AAE reflects the fact that the Niger-Congo languages spoken by the ancestors of modern speakers of African American varieties required an expressed copula in this position, whereas those same Niger-Congo languages usually had no copula before adjectives, which contributed to the high rate of deletion (or frequent absence) of copulas before adjectives in the modern creoles and AAE.

Labov eventually came to support this interpretation of the data; citing the work of Bailey (1966) and other creolists, including my own, he concluded that "Scholars who remained skeptical about the Creole origins of Black English up to this point will concede that here is objective evidence for the gradual development of the current dialect from a Creole history" (Labov 1982: 189).

3 Expanding the data base

Writing the chapter on syntax for *Pidgins and Creoles* (Holm 1988-89) gave me an opportunity to learn more about copula patterns, but this was largely confined to the Atlantic creoles. However, it also gave me an opportunity to learn more about the many other syntactic structures that distinguish this group of creoles from their European lexical source languages, providing a framework for the research project that eventually resulted in *Comparative Creole Syntax* (Holm and Patrick, eds. 2007). This was first organized as a graduate seminar that I taught in 1992 in the City University of New York's Ph.D. Program in Linguistics. I had the good fortune to have some very talented, hard-working doctoral students who were native speakers of a number of creoles or their lexical-source languages, and every week they would present an analysis of a different area of the syntax of the creole they had chosen, so that everyone would discuss, for example, plural markers one week or pronouns the next. Over the following semesters the seminar was repeated with new students, and other scholars joined the project, many becoming the contributors of the chapters of Holm and Patrick, eds. (2007). Together we wrote and presented a number of conference papers, one of which — published as Holm *et al.* (1999) — was on copulas. This gave us our first chance to compare the copula patterns of Atlantic creoles with those of non-Atlantic varieties:

The inclusion of non-Atlantic creole copulas in Table 1 makes the general pattern of Atlantic creole copulas more salient by contrast: with few exceptions, the Atlantic creoles require an expressed (i.e. not a zero or deleted) equative copula before noun phrases; they have an expressed copula of a different form before locatives, but this can be deleted; they usually have no copula before adjectives; and a focus marker or highlighter of the same form as the equative copula.

The principal exceptions to this general pattern are Papiamentu and Angolar (which have a uniformly expressed copula) and Haitian and Dominican Creole French (which have a zero form throughout, except for the highlighter). Two Atlantic creoles which have expressed copulas before adjectives, Palenquero and Cape Verdean, preserve their superstrates' distinction between states that are permanent (S, P *ser*) and those that are temporary (S, P *estar*).

Tab. 1: Forms of Creole copulas in various environments (from Holm *et al.*1999: 99)

	__NP	__loc	__Adj	Highlighter
Atlantic Creoles				
Jamaican CE	a/iz	de/0	0	a/iz
Guyanese CE	a	de	0	a
Gullah CE	iz	də	0	–
Krio CE	na	de	0	na
Sranan CE	na	de	0	(d)a
Negerhollands CD	(n)a	bi(n)	mi	(n)a
Haitian CF	sé/0	0	0	se
Dominican CE	sé	0	0	sé
Palenquero CS	é/hwe	(a)ta	ta/hwe	–
Papiamentu CS/P	ta	ta	ta	ta
Cape Verdean CP	e	sta	e/sta	–
Guinea-Bissau CP	i/sedu	sta	0/sta/sedu	–
Angolar	tha	tha	tha/0	–
Non-Atlantic Creoles				
Seychelles CF	0	0	0	–
Nagamese CAs	ase/0	ase	ase/0	–
Tok Pisin C/PE	0	stap	0	em
Nubi CA	0	fí/0	0	–
Zamboanga CS	0	t-alya	0	–

4 The Atlas of Pidgin and Creole Structures (APiCS)

The recent publication of the *Atlas of Pidgin and Creole Structures* (Michaelis *et al.* eds. 2013) has made possible the broadest perspective yet on this area of creole syntax. APiCS is a book and an online data base with detailed information on 130 structural features in 76 mixed languages that are largely pidgins and creoles². The great advantage of APiCS is that

²Michaelis *et al.* (2013: xxxvii) state the following: “In deciding on the choice of features, we made ample use of inspiration from two sources: the World Atlas of Language Structures (WALS) and Comparative Creole Syntax (Holm and Patrick 2007). To a significant extent, the present work stands on the shoulders of these predecessors.”

it provides links to WALS or the *World Atlas of Language Structures* (Dryer and Haspelmath, eds. 2011), a book and an online data base surveying 144 structural features in nearly 400 of the world's languages, described by a team of some 55 linguists, many of them leading authorities. In a world made ideal for creolists, all of the 130 structural features in APiCS would be linked to the corresponding features in the creoles' substrate languages. Alas, this is not (yet) the case, but APiCS and WALS still have a wealth of intelligently organized data that will brighten the life of any creolist for many years. For example, chapter 120 in WALS is on the zero copula for predicate nominals. It informs us that out of the 386 languages surveyed, zero copulas are possible in 175 but impossible in 211. Moreover, there is a detailed discussion of different kinds of zero copulas illustrated by sample sentences.

Feature 105, found in many Atlantic creoles (i.e. those in the Caribbean area and along the west coast of Africa) but not in Indo-European languages, is also called predicate clefting: the verb is fronted and nominalized by a highlighter or focus marker and then repeated in its original position. This is a good distributional test for a creole verb that might be derived from a word from a different syntactic category in the lexical source language, e.g. Jamaican *sik* 'to be sick; to become sick' or *tiif* 'to steal' (from English *thief*). It is also a good test for a highlighter, another Atlantic creole syntactic category not found in Indo-European languages. A number of English-based creoles that were in close contact with English took on the latter's copula (probably from "*It's Jim who did it*" to emphasize that "*Jim did it*") to express focus or emphasis, and thus *is* became one of the creole "copulas" with a distinctive syntactic function.

In order to facilitate referencing and footnotes, the vertical column of language names on the lefthand margin of Table 2³ retain the numbers they have in the APiCS data base. The features, from left to right, are identified by small letters: (a) ____NP (copulas before predicate noun phrases); (b) ____Adj (copulas before predicative adjectives); (c) ____Loc (copulas before predicative locatives); (d) focus VV (focus marker with verb doubling or predicate clefting); (e) focus NP (focus markers for noun phrases). The asterisk (*) indicates the presence of a footnote at the bottom on the chart with the corresponding number and letter (e.g. 12a refers to the Bahamian [12] copula before predicate noun phrases [a]).

³This table is the product of combining the data in five APiCS chapters on particular structures: 73 (Predicate Noun Phrases), 74 (Predicate Adjectives), 75 (Predicate Locatives), 105 (Verb Doubling and Focus) and 104 (Focusing of Noun Phrases).

Tab. 2: Copulas in Atlantic Creoles and other languages discussed in APiCS.

<i>Language</i>	a ___ NP	b ___ Adj	c ___ Loc	d ___ focus VV	e ___ focus NP
1. Early Sranan	da~de~0	0~de	de~0	da	da
2. Sranan	na	0~de	de	na~a	na~a
3. Saramaccan	dá	0	de	0	we
4. Nengee	na	0~de	de	na	na
5. Creolese	a~0	0~de	de~0	a	a
6. Trinidad CrE	is	0	de~0	iz	iz
7. Vicentian Cr	a	0	de~0	a	a~iz
8. Jamaican	a	0	de~0	a	a
9. Belizean Cr	a~da	0~is	de~0	de	da
10. San Andrés CrE	da	0	de~0	da	da
11. Nicaraguan CrE	iz	0~iz	deh~0	0	iz
12. Bahamian Cr	-z* ⁴	0~is	de~0~is	0	is
13. Gullah	-z*	0~z	deh~0	0	duh
14. AAE	-z*~0	0~is	0~is	0	[is]
15. Krio	na	0	de	na	na
16. Ghanaian PE	bì	0~de	de	i bi	i bi
17. Nigerian P.	bì~na	0~de	de	nà	nà~i bi
18. Cameroon PE	bi, na	0~de	de~bi	na	na
19. Pichi	nà	0~de	de	nà	nà
20. Chinese PE	0~belong	0	got~stop	0	0
21. Singlish	0~is	0~is	0~is	0	It was NP who...
22. Tok Pisin	0	0	stap	0	NP yet
23. Bislama	se~0	0	stap	0	NP nomo
24. Norf'k	es	0~es	se~0	0	wos NP
25. Kriol	0	0~bi	0	0	NP naa

⁴ /-z/ in decreolizing varieties like Bahamian, Gullah and African American English (12a, 13a, 14a) is an abstraction not only for the contracted forms of the English copula with third person singular pronouns (he's, she's, it's) but also its forms for other persons such as I'm. Following general instructions in APiCS (e.g. Michaelis *et al.* eds. 2013 for feature 75, predicative locative phrases) the issue of whether there is variation or not in the form of the copula does not consider tense variants from the superstrate relevant, nor should variants for person be so considered.

Tab. 2: Copulas in Atlantic Creoles and other languages discussed in APiCS.

	a	b	c	d	e
26. Hawai'i Cr	0	0~was	stɛ	0	NP da wan hu...
27. Negerhollands	a~0	mi	bi~0	a	Di a wes NP
28. Berbice Dutch	da	0	jenda	da	da
29. Afrikaans	is	is	is	0	NP is dit wat...
30. CVC Santiago	ê	ê/sta	sta	0	Ê NP ki.../Undi [ê] ki...
31. CVC Brava	ê	e	sta	0	E NP ki...
32. CVC São Vicente	e	e	ta	0	NP e k / Foi~era NP k...
33. Guinea-Bissau Kriyol	i	0~i	sta	ku	(i) NP kin ki...
34. Casamance Cr	i	0~i	sa	0	(i) NP ki...
35. Santome	sa	0~sa	sa	so	NP so
36. Angolar	tha~0	0~tha	tha	thô	NP thô ki...
37. Principense	sa~0	0~sa	a~0	êli ki	NP êli ki...
38. Fa d'Ambô	sa~0	0~sa	sa	?	amu-se
39. Diu Indo-Port.	ɛ	ɛ~te	te	0	NP ki
40. Korlai	tɛ~0 [rare]	tɛ	tə~ti	?	NP ki ti
41. Sri Lanka Port.	0~teen~mee	0~teem	teem~tinha	0	NP mee
42. Papia Kristang	0~teng	0	0	0	F<-teng NP
43. Batavia Cr	0	teng	teng	?	NP ki
44. Ternate Chab.	0	0	ta	0	NP kel
45. Cavite Chab.	0	0	ta	0	NPque
46. Zamboanga Chab.	0~estába~amó	0~estába~amó	0~está(ba)	0	amó
47. Papiamentu	ta	ta	ta	ta~0	F< -(ta) NP
48. Palenquero	e~ta~fue~era~sendá* ⁵	é~ta~fue~sendá*	ta~a~ta	0	F<-era NP
49. Haitian Cr	se	0	0	se	F<-(se) NP ki
50. Guadeloupean Cr	0~sé	0	0~ye	sé~0	F<-sé NP ki
51. Martinican Cr	0~sé	0	0~ye	0	F<-sé NP ki
52. Guyanais	sa	0	fika	a	F<-a NP ki
53. Louisiana Cr	se~0* ⁶	0~se	0~se	0	F<-se NP ki
54. Reunion Cr	sé~lé	le	le	0	F<-sé NP lé

⁵Although these forms (48a, b) are personal and tense variants of the two distinct copulas *ser* and *estar* in Spanish, the data in APiCS indicate that this may not be the case in Palenquero.

⁶The zero form of the copula can only occur after a negator.

Tab. 2: Copulas in Atlantic Creoles and other languages discussed in APiCS.

	a	b	c	d	e
55. Mauritian Cr	0	0	0	0	F<-NP (mem) ki
56. Seychelles Cr	0	0	0	0	F<-NP (menm~sa) ki
57. Tayo	0	0~le	le* ⁷	0	F<-se NP le
58. Kikongo-Kituba	ke	kele	ke~vand-aka	ku___?	si NP
59. Sango	ke	a-ke	ke~a-ke	V~ngo	NP laa~si
60. Lingala	0	a-zal-í	a-zal-i	?	F<-NP moto
61. Fanakalo	0	0	khon-a	0	?
62. Mixed Ma'a/Mbugu	ni	ní	é-re-áta	0	si NP
63. Kinubi	de~0	0~kun	0-gi-kún	0	F<-NP RelC
64. Juba Arabic	0	0	fi	0	F<-NPyáwu RelC
65. Chinese P Russian	0	0	sidi	?	?
66. Sri Lankan Malay	0	0	a-dhuudhung* ⁸	0	NP jo
67. Sing. Bazaar Malay	0	0	0	0	F<-itu
68. Ambon Malay	0	0	0	0	itu NP
69. Yimas-Arafundi Pd.	anak	anak	tandaukə-nan	?	?
70. Pd. Hindustani	baito	0	baito	0	?
71. Pd. Hawaiian	0	0	0~noho	0	F<-NP no
72. Gurindji Kriol	see APiCS	0~top	im top*	0	datsda NP
73. Media Lingua	0~ga-	ga-	ga--0 ⁹	0	see APiCS
74. Chinuk Wawa	0	0	mitlayt	0	?
75. Michif	see APiCS* ¹⁰	ili~etc.	ashtee~aya-	0	see APiCS
76. Eskimo Pd.	0	0	0	?	?
Batavia CP (Tugu)	teng~0	teng~0	0		
Louis. CF (older)	cé~0	0	0		
Louis. CF (Pointe Coupée)	se~0				

⁷Tayo *le* is glossed SI but no interpretation of this abbreviation could be found.

⁸The digraph <dh> is used here for the thorn representing the voiced interdental fricative used in APiCS.

⁹*im* is the third person singular personal pronoun and here stands for any personal pronoun before *top* 'be.'

¹⁰Translation of sample sentence 75-190 for Michif: "Her father was a widow."

Of course problems arise in any attempt to organize a great deal of complex information into a very limited amount of space, such as the five slots for copula forms for each of the 76 languages included in Table 2. The data base permits a detailed discussion of these forms, but the table does not, although footnotes are possible. For example, the data base introduction to feature 75, predicative locative phrases, makes it clear what counts as a distinct form of a copula and what does not: in AAE “Mary is here” and “Mary here”, the expressed and the zero form constitute two distinct forms of the copula. However, the expressed past tense form “Mary was here” and the contracted present form “Mary’s here” are both expressed forms and therefore do not constitute additional forms of the copula for the purposes of this table. That being the case, the non-distinct forms in the APiCS data base were simply omitted from Table 2 in the present study. When there are many individuals contributing to a data base, it is easy to overlook such guidelines, as Peter Patrick and I learned in editing *Comparative Creole Syntax*, which described the grammar of only 18 creole languages. Furthermore, different languages may deal with the same phenomenon in different ways: AAE *is* and *was* refer to different tenses, but apparently Palenquero *e*, *era* and *fue* may not, so all three are retained in Table 2.

Finally, to err is human and basic to huge masses of data, but luckily data bases are more easily corrected than books. For example, one of the sample sentences for Michif (see footnote 75a) is translated as “Her father was a widow.” In English widows cannot father children, but it seems likely that it will be possible to alert APiCS editors to such errors by email, as is currently possible on the WALS database.

5 Conclusions

This brief look at a small area of creole syntax suggests some possible strategies in working out typological groupings for creole languages. Creoles have traditionally been grouped by their lexical source language, but this has led to groups (e.g. the Portuguese-based creoles) whose members may have very little to do with one another typologically. However, superstrate input can without a doubt influence creole structures: the indication of possession by juxtaposing two nouns in the order [possessor + possessed] is typical of creoles with Germanic superstrates like English and Dutch in which a genitive marker on the possessor is dropped. The APiCS data base orders the 76 mixed languages it examines by their lexifiers but also by the geographical area in which they are spoken, allowing the clustering of languages sharing similar substrates, such as the Portuguese-based creoles of Upper Guinea as opposed

to those of the Gulf of Guinea. Grouping creoles by substrate goes back at least to Schuchardt, who not only distinguished Malayo-Portuguese from Indo-Portuguese, but subdivided the latter into two branches: Gauru-Portuguese, influenced by the Indic languages, and Dravido-Portuguese, influenced by languages in the unrelated Dravidian family (Schuchardt 1889: 476).

In the present study superstrate influence on creole copulas has been mentioned in passing (e.g. the semantic distinction between Spanish and Portuguese *ser* and *estar*) and it should be clear that this study recognizes the pervasive influence of the substrate throughout the copula systems of both the Atlantic creoles and those non-Atlantic creoles for which comparable substrate data is available. This by no means excludes the possibility of other kinds of influence, such as creole-internal innovation.

The most valuable aspect of now having comparable sets of solid data on the grammatical features of 76 mixed languages is that this can throw new light on the issue of creole typologies. Creolists have already gained some valuable ground: (1) no twenty-first century creolist believes we will find a single type that will fit all of the world's creoles, and (2) there seems to be widespread agreement among contact linguists that the distinction between Atlantic creoles and other kinds of creoles is real and useful. Creolists should use the hard data now available in the APiCS database to define Atlantic creoles as languages whose copulas pattern according to the following syntactic environment as described above (including a focus marker used in verb doubling or predicate clefting); it must be stipulated that this applies only to languages whose sociolinguistic history indicates that they have undergone creolization so that the category will exclude substrate languages.

It is time to stop building typologies on educated guesses and start basing them on generalizations drawn from trustworthy data now available. Such typologies are more useful because they have predictive value, which is what science is supposed to be about.

Abbreviations

Adj: adjective; **CA**: Creole Arabic; **CAs**: Creole Assamese; **CD**: Creole Dutch; **CE**: Creole English; **CF**: Creole French; **Chab.**: Chabacano; **CP**: Creole Portuguese; **CS**: Creole Spanish; **C/PE**: Creole and Pidgin English; **CS**: Creole Spanish; **CS/P**: Creole Spanish and Portuguese; **F<-**: fronted; **Loc**: locative; **Louis.**: Louisiana; **NP**: noun phrase; **Pd**: Pidgin; **Port.**: Portuguese; **RelC**: relative clause; **Sing.**: Singapore; **V**: verb; **VV**: predicate clefting or verb doubling; **0**: not present; **___**: position of copula; **-**: bound morpheme boundary; **~** or **/** varies with; *****: see footnote below (language number plus letter of syntactic structure); see APiCS: see this item in Michaelis *et al.* eds. 2013; **?**: information not in APiCS online as of 15-07-2013).

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